

GROWTH PERFORMANCE IN THE PRODUCTION OF MAJOR OILSEEDS AMONG LEADING STATES IN INDIA

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Abstract

Oilseed group is an important cash crop group in Indian agriculture. They are the source of edible oils for the country. The oilseed group is classified into nine oilseeds which are groundnut, sunflower, soybean, rapeseed mustard, sunflower, sesame, niger, linseed and castor. Linseed and castor are considered as inedible oilseeds. India is a major producer and consumer of oilseeds and their products, emerging in the late 1990s as one of the world's largest importers of edible oils. Oilseeds are imported to meet the consumption demand of the country because despite of their increasing production the oilseed sector has shown unstable performance. The present study is therefore has examined growth in major oilseeds producing states for all the nine-oilseed using Compound annual growth rate using time series secondary sourced data. The time period of the study was taken from 1970-71 to 2017-18. The time period is further divided into phases and the basis of division is taken as before and after the implementation of Technology Mission on Oilseeds.

Keywords: Oilseeds, Growth trend, Growth performance, Production performance of oilseeds

Introduction

Oilseeds are considered as the important source of cash crops in Indian agriculture. They are the important sources of edible oils supply in the country. In all, there are mainly nine annual oilseeds crops grown namely, groundnut, rapeseed, mustard, soybean, sunflower, linseed, sesame, castor, safflower and niger. From these nine, groundnut, rapeseed and mustard, soybean, sesame and sunflower are classified as major oilseeds accounting for 89 per cent of the area and 93 per cent of the total production in oilseeds in the country (Kalra and Srivastava, 2023). The oilseeds are considered as the second largest crop group grown after the food grains in the country. India is fortunate in having a variety of oilseeds crops that are grown in the wide and rich climatic zones of India (Nayak *et al.*, 2021).

India is a major producer and consumer of oilseeds and their products, emerging in the late 1990s as one of the world's largest importers of edible oils (Reddy and Immanuelraj, 2017). About 14 million persons are engaged in the production of oil seeds and another one million is engaged in the processing sector in oilseeds. India is the third largest vegetable oil economy in the world next to the USA and China. India is also one of the largest exporters of oil meals, particularly of soybean meals which accounted for more than 70 per cent of the total exported oil meals followed by rapeseed mustard, castor, etc. India is exporting oil to large number of the countries like South East Asia (share of around 77 per cent) followed by Middle East and Africa region (around 15 per cent). Japan is considered as the largest importer of the oil meals followed by Vietnam, South Korea, Iran and Thailand from India (Indian Council of Food and Agriculture, 2020). The diverse agro-ecological conditions in the country is favourable for growing oil seeds which include seven edible oil seeds viz., groundnut, rapeseed, mustard, soybean, sunflower, sesame and niger and two non-edible sources i.e., castor and linseed. The country ranks first in the world in the production of castor, sunflower, sesame and niger, second in groundnut and rapeseed, third in linseed and fifth in soybean and sunflower. These oil seeds being raised mostly under rain fed conditions and are important for the livelihood of small and marginal farmers in the arid and semi-arid eco systems of the country. As per the third advance estimates released by the department of Food and Public Distribution under the ministry of agriculture, the oilseed production was estimated at 36.56 million tons during the year 2020-21. Alongside the considerable production progress in the oilseed sector the sector is still unstable in the nature (Debnath *et al.*, 2015). The production seems not to be

sufficient as the domestic demand of the country is still met through imports which accounts for 54 per cent. The possible reason being the unstable nature of production of oilseeds due to their rainfed nature. There are also reasons that technological advancements in the country has made crop production more sensitive to temperature and rainfall (Ray, 1983). According to (Larson *et al.* 2004) green revolution technology also have not reduced the problem of instability in the country. Therefore, the country relies more on import to meet the gap between the demand and supply. In the view of the above, this study focussed on the examination of the growth performance of oilseeds in their area and production.

Methodology

The time series data on the production of major oilseeds in major states and country as a whole on oilseeds was collected from various published and unpublished sources such as journals, official government records, department of agriculture, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare, commodities.cmie.com, etc. The time period of the study was taken from 1970-71 to 2017-18. The study time period is further divided into phases as mentioned: Pre-Technology Mission on Oilseeds (Pre TMO) Period from 1970-71 to 2017-18. Technology Mission on Oilseeds Phase one Period from 1986-87 to 2001-02. Technology Mission on Oilseeds Phase two Period from 2002-03 to 2017-18. Overall Period of Technology Mission on Oilseeds from 1986-87 to 2017-18. Overall Period from 1970-71 to 2017-18. After the introduction of Technology Mission on Oilseeds there has been a continuous increase in the production of oilseeds (Kaushik, 1993), therefore the present study is divided on the basis of TMO time period. To fulfil the objective of growth estimation, compound annual growth rate was calculated. Compound Annual Growth Rate can be mathematically written as

$$CAGR = [(1/Y_t) \cdot (dY_t / dt)] = [(Y_{t+1} - Y_t) / Y_t]$$

It is rate of change of Y_t per unit of change in time 't' expressed as a fraction of the magnitude of Y_t itself.

The CAGR has been estimated using the exponential function of the following form:

$$Y_t = Ae^{bt}$$

The log transformation of this function is as follows:

$$\text{Log}_e Y_t = \text{Log}_e A + bt$$

Through regression analysis the values of 'A' and 'b' were found

The log form of function represents a constant growth rate over time
The formula for calculating CAGR from the log liner can be derived as follows:

Let 'Y₀' be the value of the variables under study in the base period
'Y_t' be the value of the variable in the time 't' and 'r' be the value of CGR (compound growth rate).

Using compounding formula, we get,

$$Y_t = Y_0 (1 + r)^t$$

Log transformation of the above is

$$\log Y_t = \log Y_0 + t \log (1 + r)$$

Assuming $\log Y_0 = \log A$ and $\log (1 + r) = b$, the same expression can be put as :

$$\log Y_t = \log A + bt$$

The estimate of 'b' here is in log-linear form. Therefore, to convert it into original form of Y_t, following transformation is done,

$$\text{Since } b = \log (1 + r)$$

$$\text{Antilog } (b) = 1 + r$$

$$\text{Therefore: CAGR } (r) = (\text{Antilog } b) - 1$$

$$\text{CAGR in percentage} = [(\text{Antilog } b) - 1] * 100$$

Results and Discussions:

The results of growth in the production of oilseeds in India and major oilseed producing states for the given periods are presented below.

Compound annual growth in production of groundnut during different periods.

Compound annual growth rates of groundnut production for different periods are presented in the table 1. The table depicts that during Pre TMO-period production of groundnut increased significantly in the states of West Bengal, and Karnataka at 12.44 and 1.29 per cent per annum, respectively, in which West Bengal has shown maximum rate of increase in the production of groundnut during this period. Other states during this period as well as the country as a whole have shown decline in the production, highest rate of decline has been shown in Kerala at the rate of 6.09 per cent per annum. During overall study period, West Bengal, Gujarat, Tamil Nadu and Rajasthan along with India have shown positive growth in which maximum increase has been found in the state of West Bengal at the rate of 14.22 per cent per annum. Technology Mission on Oilseeds has shown positive impact in the production of groundnut in the states of West Bengal, Gujarat, Rajasthan and Tamil Nadu.

Table 1: Compound annual growth of groundnut production for different periods (production, 000' tons)

States /Country	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Gujarat	Pre TMO	1835.90	448.2	7.08	-0.010**	0.03	0.70	-0.99
	TMO (I)	1291.70	2646.60	6.75	0.046*	0.04	0.76	4.78
	TMO (II)	1094.50	3937.10	7.59	0.026*	0.02	0.59	2.67
	TMO Total	1291.70	3937.10	6.81	0.040**	0.01	0.25	4.12
	Overall Period	1835.90	3937.10	6.87	0.020**	0.006	0.69	2.10
Maharashtra	Pre TMO	616.60	468.70	6.06	-0.028*	0.01	0.38	-2.76
	TMO (I)	435.20	492.20	6.67	0.012	0.01	0.16	1.20
	TMO (II)	450.00	344.30	6.12	-0.017**	0.006	0.32	-1.76
	TMO Total	435.20	344.30	6.70	-0.028**	0.003	0.65	-2.83
	Overall Period	616.60	344.30	6.49	-0.009**	0.003	0.27	-0.96
West Bengal	Pre TMO	1.23	10.20	-0.66	0.117***	0.040	0.37	12.44
	TMO (I)	14.30	55.70	2.84	0.068***	0.009	0.77	7.09
	TMO (II)	47.30	165.20	4.11	0.077***	0.010	0.80	8.03
	TMO Total	14.30	165.20	2.75	0.081***	0.003	0.94	8.47
	Overall Period	1.23	165.20	-0.41	0.132***	0.006	0.89	14.22
Karnataka	Pre TMO	613.10	707.10	6.29	0.012*	0.012	0.70	1.29
	TMO (I)	738.10	585.80	6.89	-0.004*	0.012	0.65	-0.48
	TMO (II)	539.00	552.60	6.37	-0.014	0.012	0.08	-1.40
	TMO Total	738.10	552.60	5.88	-0.019*	0.020	0.60	-1.93
	Overall Period	613.10	552.60	6.61	-0.004*	0.003	0.35	-0.42
Tamil Nadu	Pre TMO	916.70	1176.00	6.95	-0.004*	0.009	0.53	-0.40
	TMO (I)	1092.60	1250.00	7.17	-0.00001	0.020	0.0000005	-0.001
	TMO (II)	717.40	1007.50	6.88	0.027*	0.008	0.38	2.73
	TMO Total	192.60	1007.50	7.28	0.017**	0.005	0.25	1.71
	Overall Period	916.70	1007.50	7.05	0.013*	0.002	0.45	1.30
Uttar Pradesh + Uttarakhand	Pre TMO	221.70	105.30	5.76	-0.060***	0.017	0.45	-5.86
	TMO (I)	110.60	90.20	4.77	-0.010*	0.010	0.70	-1.04
	TMO (II)	50.05	89.10	4.10	0.024***	0.008	0.35	2.45
	TMO Total	110.60	89.10	4.75	-0.015***	0.004	0.30	-1.56
	Overall Period	221.70	89.10	5.43	-0.028***	0.003	0.65	-2.76
Kerala	Pre TMO	16.10	6.00	3.10	-0.062***	0.011	0.68	-6.09
	TMO (I)	6.10	1.80	2.47	-0.057*	0.027	0.33	-5.61
	TMO (II)	1.10	0.40	1.02	-0.096***	0.022	0.57	-9.23
	TMO Total	6.10	0.40	2.78	-0.102***	0.009	0.80	-9.78
	Overall Period	16.10	0.40	3.39	-0.074***	0.005	0.82	-7.13
Rajasthan	Pre TMO	6111.10	5119.50	8.61	-0.006*	0.008	0.39	-0.59

	TMO (I)	5875.40	7027.50	8.92	0.030*	0.009	0.65	-3.04
	TMO (II)	4121.10	9252.60	8.69	0.017*	0.013	0.61	1.79
	TMO Total	5875.40	9252.60	8.88	0.074*	0.004	0.59	7.68
	Overall Period	6111.10	9252.60	8.66	0.005***	0.002	0.45	0.57
	Pre TMO	105698.00	95863.00	3.23	-0.030***	0.006	0.63	-2.95
India	TMO (I)	105369.00	115698.00	2.63	0.045***	0.004	0.86	4.60
	TMO (II)	116987.00	126378.00	1.99	0.016***	0.003	0.75	1.61
	TMO Total	105369.00	126378.00	4.56	0.039***	0.002	0.69	3.97
	Overall Period	105698.00	126378.00	3.96	0.036***	0.004	0.67	3.66

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability

** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

the production of groundnut in West Bengal is from 1980-81 as data was not available for the previous time period

Compound annual growth of soybean production during different periods

Table 2 shows compound annual growth rate of soybean production in major producing states during the given periods. During the entire TMO period, Maharashtra has shown highest rate of positive growth among

all the other states at 15.42 per cent per annum. Maharashtra remained at highest in the overall study period in the positive growth rate in the production of soybean at 19.24 per cent per annum. Maharashtra, Karnataka and Madhya Pradesh (undivided) performed better than the country average during the overall period of study.

Table 2: Compound annual growth rate in production of soybean for different periods (000' tons)

States /country	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Maharashtra	Pre TMO	5.25	16.66	1.56	0.075***	0.004	0.94	7.88
	TMO (I)	19.80	1385.50	3.37	0.288***	0.026	0.89	33.41
	TMO (II)	1576.00	3804.80	7.63	0.042**	0.016	0.31	4.37
	TMO Total	19.80	3804.80	4.45	0.143***	0.013	0.78	15.42
	Overall Period	1576.00	3804.80	1.03	0.175***	0.007	0.92	19.24
Karnataka	Pre TMO	5.63	3.65	1.63	-0.042**	0.019	0.25	-4.13
	TMO (I)	4.00	40.20	1.48	0.182***	0.026	0.76	19.96
	TMO (II)	47.80	252.90	3.88	0.106***	0.013	0.85	11.23
	TMO Total	4.00	252.90	1.95	0.118***	0.008	0.86	12.56
	Overall Period	5.63	252.90	0.41	0.106***	0.006	0.87	11.26
Gujarat	Pre TMO	2.50	1.00	1.23	-0.0008	0.033	0.0004	-0.087
	TMO (I)	6.00	5.10	2.48	-0.045	0.028	0.15	-4.44
	TMO (II)	10.00	115.50	2.52	0.128***	0.021	0.71	13.68
	TMO Total	6.00	115.50	0.61	0.069***	0.006	0.68	7.18
	Overall Period	2.50	115.50	1.50	0.081***	0.012	0.58	8.52
Rajasthan	Pre TMO	123.40	2492.00	4.90	0.186***	0.010	0.95	20.52
	TMO (I)	3386.90	10968.20	8.25	0.054***	0.009	0.68	5.55
	TMO (II)	9905.40	11678.27	9.17	0.004*	0.007	0.67	0.42
	TMO Total	3386.90	11678.27	8.42	0.036***	0.003	0.75	3.76
	Overall Period	123.40	11678.27	6.01	0.088***	0.005	0.83	9.24
Madhya Pradesh + Chhattisgarh	Pre TMO	3021.12	3469.45	4.56	0.007***	0.004	0.78	0.70
	TMO (I)	3924.66	14376.01	4.29	0.096***	0.001	0.83	10.07
	TMO (II)	14796.29	16783.63	8.39	0.074***	0.002	0.74	7.68
	TMO Total	3924.66	16783.63	8.99	0.085***	0.003	0.83	8.87
	Overall Period	3021.12	16783.63	8.76	0.094***	0.004	0.96	9.85
India	Pre TMO	534.09	7536.75	8.43	0.086***	0.003	0.82	8.98
	TMO (I)	19643.12	27569.26	8.08	0.074***	0.004	0.75	7.68
	TMO (II)	30432.15	35635.29	6.96	0.080***	0.002	0.74	8.32
	TMO Total	19643.12	35635.29	9.09	0.092***	0.001	0.89	9.63
	Overall Period	534.09	35635.29	9.72	0.091***	0.004	0.94	9.52

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability

** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

Compound annual growth of rapeseed and mustard production during different periods.

Table 3 presents growth in the production of rapeseed and mustard for different periods. During the entire study period, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu production remained stable and rest other states and country's production grew significantly except in Uttar Pradesh where

production declined at the rate of 0.68 per cent per annum. During this period, maximum growth rate in production registered by Madhya Pradesh (undivided) at the rate of 7.35 per cent per annum.

Table 3: Compound annual growth rate in production of rapeseed and mustard for different periods (000'tons)

States	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Gujarat	Pre TMO	16.30	208.90	2.35	0.16***	0.016	0.91	2.11
	TMO (I)	234.90	292.10	5.77	0.009	0.016	0.02	1.00
	TMO (II)	172.30	399.60	5.88	0.05*	0.015	0.80	5.12
	TMO Total	234.90	399.60	5.82	0.002*	0.005	0.70	0.29
	Overall Period	16.30	399.60	3.76	0.06***	0.006	0.62	6.24
Maharashtra	Pre TMO	0.90	1.40	-0.32	0.058***	0.009	0.73	6.02
	TMO (I)	2.70	3.00	0.64	0.035	0.026	0.11	3.62
	TMO (II)	2.00	2.20	1.13	0.008	0.017	0.015	0.80
	TMO Total	2.70	2.20	0.85	0.008	0.007	0.04	0.89
	Overall Period	0.90	2.20	0.04	0.027	0.004	0.50	2.82
West Bengal	Pre TMO	35.70	163.40	3.17	0.105***	0.015	0.77	11.18
	TMO (I)	176.90	336.90	5.60	0.007*	0.010	0.45	0.79
	TMO (II)	328.50	722.60	5.78	0.032**	0.007	0.56	3.28
	TMO Total	176.90	722.60	5.48	0.022***	0.003	0.60	2.32
	Overall Period	35.70	722.60	3.78	0.060***	0.004	0.81	6.23
Karnataka	Pre TMO	1.60	1.10	-0.30	0.012	0.015	0.04	-1.24
	TMO (I)	0.80	1.90	-0.03	0.044***	0.006	0.76	4.56
	TMO (II)	1.10	0.30	0.82	-0.085**	0.025	0.45	-8.23
	TMO Total	0.80	0.30	0.49	-0.016	0.008	0.11	-1.67
	Overall Period	1.60	0.30	-0.09	0.007*	0.004	0.45	0.71
Tamil Nadu	Pre TMO	0.10	0.20	-1.92	0.031	0.015	0.24	3.21
	TMO (I)	0.20	0.10	-1.63	0.008	0.027	0.005	0.80
	TMO (II)	0.10	0.10	-2.53	0.044	0.030	0.13	4.50
	TMO Total	0.20	0.10	-1.51	-0.021	0.011	0.10	-2.09
	Overall Period	0.10	0.10	-1.52	-0.010	0.005	0.08	-1.09
Uttar Pradesh + Uttarakhand	Pre TMO	1313.50	658.90	7.11	-0.026**	0.009	0.36	-2.62
	TMO (I)	594.60	845.40	6.72	0.014*	0.011	0.63	1.43
	TMO (II)	759.10	945.20	6.74	0.008*	0.008	0.60	-0.83
	TMO Total	594.60	945.20	6.87	0.007*	0.003	0.56	-0.71
	Overall Period	1313.50	945.20	6.97	-0.006**	0.002	0.42	-0.68
Rajasthan	Pre TMO	1975.30	2680.50	7.32	0.032**	0.009	0.45	3.28
	TMO (I)	2604.70	5082.60	8.24	0.028**	0.010	0.31	2.84
	TMO (II)	3879.80	8429.80	8.68	0.019*	0.009	0.45	1.93
	TMO Total	2604.70	8429.80	8.29	0.022***	0.003	0.58	2.30
	Overall Period	1975.30	8429.80	7.39	0.037***	0.002	0.84	3.82
Madhya Pradesh + Chhattisgarh	Pre TMO	1536.03	1763.03	6.36	0.034***	0.002	0.75	3.45
	TMO (I)	1796.36	5632.03	7.03	0.056***	0.001	0.74	5.75
	TMO (II)	5697.36	9617.33	7.63	0.059***	0.004	0.86	6.07
	TMO Total	1796.36	9617.33	8.96	0.067***	0.006	0.89	6.92
	Overall Period	1536.03	9617.33	8.43	0.071***	0.007	0.91	7.35
India	Pre TMO	6532.03	7563.66	8.45	0.035***	0.003	0.67	3.56
	TMO (I)	7769.31	13496.96	8.96	0.044***	0.002	0.71	4.49
	TMO (II)	13659.75	23154.39	7.91	0.059***	0.001	0.80	6.07
	TMO Total	7769.31	23154.39	8.06	0.053***	0.003	0.89	5.44
	Overall Period	6532.03	23154.39	8.75	0.069***	0.007	0.94	7.14

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability ** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

Compound annual growth in production of linseed during different periods

Compound annual growth rate in the production of linseed across major states for different periods is given in table 4. During the overall study period, all the states along with India have observed decline in the production with highest negative growth in West Bengal to the tune of 5.77

per cent per annum. Like decline in linseed area in the country its production also declines in TMO period. The rate of decline in its production was sharper in the phase II of TMO compared to that of in the TMO phase I.

Table 4: Compound annual growth rate in production of linseed for different periods (000'tons)

States	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Maharashtra	Pre TMO	36.70	54.00	5.92	0.027**	0.011	0.30	2.81

	TMO (I)	39.10	21.00	6.18	-0.043**	0.008	0.65	-4.20
	TMO (II)	12.00	3.20	6.89	-0.06*	0.014	0.43	-5.82
	TMO Total	39.10	3.20	4.18	-0.083***	0.005	0.86	-7.98
	Overall Period	36.70	3.20	5.96	-0.023***	0.002	0.68	-2.32
	Pre TMO	1.10	0.70	0.20	-0.048**	0.016	0.38	-4.70
Punjab	TMO (I)	0.60	0.30	-0.80	-0.006	0.026	0.03	-0.62
	TMO (II)	0.20	0.19	-2.05	-0.007	0.019	0.01	-0.79
	TMO Total	0.60	0.19	-0.54	-0.053***	0.009	0.49	-5.17
	Overall Period	1.10	0.19	0.24	-0.051***	0.004	0.72	-5.01
Uttar Pradesh	Pre TMO	201.30	70.50	5.41	-0.067**	0.016	0.53	-6.53
	TMO (I)	60.20	38.40	4.39	-0.032**	0.006	0.63	-3.23
	TMO (II)	36.90	15.70	3.64	-0.078**	0.017	0.58	-7.57
	TMO Total	60.20	15.70	4.65	-0.067***	0.005	0.85	-6.49
	Overall Period	201.30	15.70	5.40	-0.058***	0.003	0.88	-5.65
West Bengal	Pre TMO	13.20	13.20	2.65	0.009	0.010	0.05	0.94
	TMO (I)	6.80	4.70	1.38	-0.010*	0.020	0.01	-0.99
	TMO (II)	3.70	2.50	0.55	-0.003	0.017	0.003	-0.29
	TMO Total	6.80	2.50	1.50	-0.034***	0.007	0.42	-3.36
	Overall Period	13.20	2.50	2.99	-0.059***	0.004	0.77	-5.77
Karnataka	Pre TMO	12.70	4.00	2.70	-0.026*	0.028	0.50	-2.61
	TMO (I)	9.80	6.60	2.17	-0.024**	0.010	0.27	-2.39
	TMO (II)	6.10	0.70	1.63	-0.085**	0.028	0.38	-8.15
	TMO Total	9.80	0.70	2.48	-0.063***	0.007	0.67	-6.10
	Overall Period	12.70	0.70	2.97	-0.048***	0.004	0.68	-4.37
Rajasthan	Pre TMO	473.80	376.20	6.28	-0.020*	0.009	0.45	-2.01
	TMO (I)	316.30	209.10	5.95	-0.033***	0.005	0.72	-3.33
	TMO (II)	176.10	173.80	5.17	-0.010	0.005	0.21	-1.08
	TMO Total	316.30	173.80	4.66	-0.025*	0.004	0.63	-2.46
	Overall Period	473.80	173.80	6.37	-0.030***	0.001	0.89	-3.04
India	Pre TMO	1043.29	759.79	5.29	-0.035***	0.021	0.75	-3.43
	TMO (I)	797.69	597.86	4.06	-0.029***	0.001	0.69	-2.85
	TMO (II)	579.00	347.98	4.00	-0.041***	0.010	0.72	-4.01
	TMO Total	797.69	347.98	4.29	-0.030***	0.002	0.69	-2.95
	Overall Period	1043.29	347.98	6.07	-0.053***	0.004	0.70	-5.16

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability

** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

Compound annual growth of linseed production during different periods

Compound annual growth rate in the production of sunflower crop is shown in table 5. It is observed that the rate of decline or the rate of increase per year, as the case may be, in different major states as well as in the country as a whole was more in TMO I compared to that of in TMO II period of study.

Table 5: Compound annual growth rate in production of sunflower for different periods (000'tons)

States	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Karnataka	Pre TMO	30.15	120.10	2.85	0.110**	0.031	0.44	11.67
	TMO (I)	290.10	262.40	5.81	-0.009	0.018	0.01	-0.90
	TMO (II)	374.00	106.90	6.62	-0.11***	0.017	0.72	-10.44
	TMO Total	290.10	106.90	5.99	-0.017*	0.008	0.45	-1.69
	Overall Period	30.15	106.90	3.78	0.052***	0.008	0.45	5.37
Maharashtra	Pre TMO	32.01	135.50	2.00	0.153**	0.060	0.31	16.58
	TMO (I)	83.60	130.70	5.24	0.008*	0.022	0.55	0.81
	TMO (II)	143.00	22.20	5.72	-0.166***	0.027	0.71	-15.31
	TMO Total	83.60	22.20	5.91	-0.067***	0.011	0.51	-6.48
	Overall Period	32.01	22.20	3.63	0.027**	0.012	0.52	2.78
Punjab	Pre TMO	36.00	57.26	3.34	0.039**	0.012	0.40	4.04
	TMO (I)	34.85	10.50	4.07	-0.004*	0.056	0.39	-0.40
	TMO (II)	22.00	10.50	3.74	-0.073**	0.016	0.58	-7.10

	TMO Total	34.85	10.50	4.45	-0.053**	0.014	0.30	-5.16
	Overall Period	36.00	10.50	4.03	-0.017**	0.007	0.46	-1.70
Tamil Nadu	Pre TMO	57.80	7.00	4.44	-0.158**	0.005	0.36	-14.62
	TMO (I)	8.20	9.00	2.71	0.007	0.026	0.006	0.79
	TMO (II)	8.90	6.00	3.45	-0.085**	0.037	0.26	-8.18
	TMO Total	8.20	6.00	2.95	-0.011	0.012	0.03	-1.18
	Overall Period	57.80	6.00	3.33	-0.019**	0.008	0.85	-1.88
	Rajasthan	Pre TMO	137.60	1193.80	4.04	0.176***	0.027	0.74
TMO (I)		1181.70	1463.10	6.94	0.04*	0.015	0.46	4.32
TMO (II)		1158.00	150.30	6.85	-0.11***	0.013	0.84	-11.20
TMO Total		1181.70	150.30	7.49	-0.066***	0.007	0.73	-6.46
Overall Period		137.60	150.30	5.86	0.010*	0.009	0.43	1.03
Madhya Pradesh + Chhattisgarh	Pre TMO	286.46	1763.19	4.12	0.043***	0.002	0.49	4.39
	TMO (I)	1786.04	2175.63	5.02	0.039***	0.001	0.59	3.97
	TMO (II)	1765.63	4364.03	5.12	0.052***	0.003	0.63	5.33
	TMO Total	1786.04	4364.03	5.63	0.042***	0.004	0.48	4.28
	Overall Period	286.46	4364.03	5.79	0.050***	0.001	0.67	5.12
India	Pre TMO	786.03	3975.63	5.96	0.059***	0.001	0.64	6.07
	TMO (I)	4129.03	5976.00	4.23	0.040***	0.003	0.53	4.08
	TMO (II)	4043.01	4976.02	3.99	0.039***	0.004	0.57	3.97
	TMO Total	4129.03	4976.02	3.68	0.027***	0.007	0.54	2.73
	Overall Period	786.03	4976.02	5.78	0.062	0.004	0.75	6.39

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability

** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

Compound annual growth of castor production during different periods

Compound annual growth rate in the production of castor is presented in table 6. During the overall TMO period, only Gujarat, Rajasthan and country as a whole realized positive growth in the production where Gujarat performed well as compared to Rajasthan and the country at 5.95 per cent per annum rate of growth while rest of the other states have shown decline in the production with highest rate of decline in Tamil Nadu to the extent of 7.05 per cent per annum. During overall period of study, all the states have shown positive growth in production except in Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Punjab where production declined at the rate of 1.44, 2.00 and 1.58 per cent per annum, respectively. During this period, highest increase in the production registered in Gujarat at the rate of 7.38 per cent per annum. Gujarat, Rajasthan and the country as a whole recorded growth in castor production during all the phases under study.

Table 6: Compound annual growth rate in production of castor for different periods (000'tons)

States	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Gujarat	Pre TMO	38.80	202.30	3.42	0.148***	0.012	0.91	15.98
	TMO (I)	129.30	465.10	5.22	0.099**	0.025	0.52	10.45
	TMO (II)	283.10	1333.30	6.01	0.091***	0.013	0.75	9.57
	TMO Total	129.30	1333.30	5.47	0.057***	0.008	0.63	5.95
	Overall Period	38.80	1333.30	4.10	0.071***	0.004	0.84	7.38
Karnataka	Pre TMO	14.40	18.80	2.79	0.009	0.014	0.02	0.90
	TMO (I)	24.30	16.10	3.00	-0.007*	0.015	0.39	-0.75
	TMO (II)	15.70	4.70	3.30	-0.100***	0.015	0.75	-9.56
	TMO Total	24.30	4.70	3.42	-0.040***	0.007	0.51	-3.94
	Overall Period	14.40	4.70	3.15	-0.014**	0.004	0.19	-1.44
Maharashtra	Pre TMO	0.70	1.50	-0.37	0.071***	0.012	0.68	7.36
	TMO (I)	1.80	3.10	0.49	0.044***	0.007	0.72	4.52
	TMO (II)	7.00	1.40	1.67	-0.044*	0.021	0.63	-4.32
	TMO Total	1.80	1.40	0.75	-0.020	0.007	0.21	-2.02
	Overall Period	0.70	1.40	0.01	0.032***	0.003	0.62	3.27
Punjab	Pre TMO	120.32	136.52	1.20	0.014*	0.002	0.42	1.40
	TMO (I)	162.32	253.36	1.13	0.016**	0.003	0.56	1.40
	TMO (II)	123	137	0.53	0.04	0.004	0.15	1.61
	TMO Total	162.32	137	1.63	-0.015*	0.005	0.49	-1.48
	Overall Period	120.32	137	1.75	-0.016*	0.002	0.59	-1.58
Tamil Nadu	Pre TMO	3.60	4.20	1.26	0.014*	0.012	0.45	1.44
	TMO (I)	4.80	8.00	2.00	0.017*	0.010	0.55	1.74
	TMO (II)	5.60	1.40	1.14	-0.054**	0.013	0.53	-5.26
	TMO Total	4.80	1.40	2.62	-0.073***	0.007	0.74	-7.05

	Overall Period	5.60	1.40	1.90	-0.020**	0.006	0.18	-2.00
Rajasthan	Pre TMO	136.10	308.30	4.84	0.069***	0.010	0.76	1.03
	TMO (I)	230.30	652.60	5.76	0.074**	0.016	0.59	7.71
	TMO (II)	427.50	1567.60	6.43	0.076***	0.013	0.68	1.07
	TMO Total	230.30	1567.60	5.89	0.051***	0.005	0.72	5.26
	Overall Period	136.10	1567.60	4.97	0.054***	0.002	0.89	1.05
India	Pre TMO	536.03	623.00	4.23	0.023***	0.002	0.59	2.32
	TMO (I)	603.22	1603.00	5.06	0.034***	0.001	0.62	3.45
	TMO (II)	1463.00	3263.00	4.90	0.042***	0.003	0.69	4.28
	TMO Total	603.22	3263.00	5.55	0.051***	0.004	0.72	5.23
	Overall Period	536.03	3263.00	6.00	0.055***	0.005	0.80	5.65

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability

** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

Compound annual growth of niger production during different periods

Compound annual growth rate of niger production is presented in table 7. In all the time phases of study niger production grew in India and the major states of Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Madhya Pradesh (undivided) and Gujarat among the major producing states.

Table 7: Compound annual growth rate in production of niger for different periods (000'tons)

States	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Karnataka	Pre TMO	3.40	9.80	1.58	0.060**	0.014	0.56	6.19
	TMO (I)	9.00	7.00	2.27	-0.018*	0.005	0.49	-1.86
	TMO (II)	5.60	0.90	2.34	-0.110**	0.026	0.54	-10.43
	TMO Total	9.00	0.90	2.57	-0.049***	0.007	0.56	-4.80
	Overall Period	3.40	0.90	2.40	-0.021***	0.005	0.28	-2.15
Maharashtra	Pre TMO	14.00	20.70	2.20	0.056**	0.020	0.36	5.81
	TMO (I)	10.80	9.50	3.01	-0.015	0.012	0.09	-1.53
	TMO (II)	14.00	2.10	3.31	-0.141***	0.026	0.67	-13.15
	TMO Total	10.80	2.10	3.41	-0.055***	0.009	0.53	-5.37
	Overall Period	14.00	2.10	3.03	-0.019**	0.006	0.48	-1.90
West Bengal	Pre TMO	1.23	2.20	-0.55	0.054	0.033	0.15	5.62
	TMO (I)	2.10	3.60	0.81	0.038***	0.006	0.69	3.95
	TMO (II)	3.60	3.20	1.36	-0.025**	0.009	0.32	-2.56
	TMO Total	2.10	3.20	1.12	0.001	0.004	0.004	0.16
	Overall Period	1.23	3.20	-0.17	0.037***	0.005	0.51	3.77
Andhra Pradesh	Pre TMO	34.23	44.32	0.32	0.042**	0.005	0.63	1.12
	TMO (I)	45.63	59.63	1.32	0.032**	0.003	0.42	1.23
	TMO (II)	60.21	78.00	1.33	0.042**	0.004	0.43	1.32
	TMO Total	45.63	78.00	1.02	0.096**	0.003	0.52	3.01
	Overall Period	34.23	78.00	1.63	0.072**	0.04	0.63	1.01
Assam	Pre TMO	3.23	4.65	2.01	0.063**	0.006	0.42	3.33
	TMO (I)	6.77	16.96	2.00	0.075**	0.007	0.44	4.32
	TMO (II)	17.65	43.63	1.32	0.042***	0.002	0.34	5.36
	TMO Total	6.77	43.63	1.96	0.03**	0.001	0.46	6.33
	Overall Period	3.23	43.63	1.65	0.036**	0.001	0.42	0.31
Madhya Pradesh+ Chhattisgarh	Pre TMO	76.32	79.63	0.63	0.042***	0.001	0.62	3.21
	TMO (I)	80.63	120.66	1.32	0.085**	0.003	0.42	2.03
	TMO (II)	112.36	130.30	2.63	0.063****	0.004	0.62	1.63
	TMO Total	80.63	130.30	6.32	0.042***	0.001	0.36	2.63
	Overall Period	76.32	130.30	1.42	0.023***	0.006	0.43	3.31
Gujarat	Pre TMO	4.62	14.63	1.33	0.042***	0.004	0.36	1.36
	TMO (I)	4.99	10.65	1.00	0.032***	0.003	0.64	2.66
	TMO (II)	11.36	20.55	1.30	0.032***	0.007	0.36	2.33
	TMO Total	4.99	20.55	3.42	0.032***	0.009	0.32	2.63

	Overall Period	4.62	20.55	4.63	0.23**	0.004	0.31	3.06
Bihar + Jharkhand	Pre TMO	127.70	192.30	4.70	0.023**	0.008	0.34	2.39
	TMO (I)	131.20	129.90	5.24	-0.019**	0.008	0.29	1.94
	TMO (II)	186.20	70.20	4.77	-0.023**	0.006	0.46	-2.36
	TMO Total	131.20	70.20	5.30	-0.028***	0.002	0.79	-2.85
	Overall Period	127.70	70.20	5.10	-0.002**	0.002	0.76	-1.00
India	Pre TMO	426.03	579.26	4.02	0.025*	0.001	0.52	2.53
	TMO (I)	597.26	625.03	4.00	0.030*	0.002	0.57	3.04
	TMO (II)	666.03	705.23	3.09	0.027*	0.001	0.51	2.73
	TMO Total	597.26	705.23	4.95	0.022*	0.005	0.62	2.22
	Overall Period	426.03	705.23	5.01	0.032*	0.004	0.67	3.25

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability

** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

Compound annual growth of sesame production during different periods

Compound annual growth rate in the production of sesame crop is presented in table 8. During the entire study period, Gujarat, West Bengal and Karnataka and Madhya Pradesh (undivided) as well as the country witnessed positive growth in the production of sesame while other states have shown negative growth wherein highest decline observed in the state of Orissa (7.35 per cent per annum)

Table 8: Compound annual growth rate in production of sesame for different periods (000'tons)

States	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Gujarat	Pre TMO	52.10	19.60	3.38	0.005*	0.022	0.36	0.51
	TMO (I)	12.20	226.60	2.61	0.181**	0.057	0.41	19.90
	TMO (II)	123.20	72.70	5.05	-0.050**	0.020	0.29	-4.90
	TMO Total	12.20	72.20	3.77	0.036*	0.018	0.71	3.71
	Overall Period	52.10	72.20	3.14	0.037***	0.008	0.29	3.78
Karnataka	Pre TMO	23.10	39.70	3.08	0.040**	0.014	0.36	4.09
	TMO (I)	37.10	27.10	4.06	-0.027**	0.015	0.26	-2.73
	TMO (II)	29.30	23.80	3.93	-0.048	0.018	0.35	-4.69
	TMO Total	37.10	23.80	4.07	-0.023**	0.005	0.37	-2.35
	Overall Period	23.10	23.80	3.55	0.001	0.003	0.003	0.15
West Bengal	Pre TMO	5.90	44.00	1.75	0.164***	0.018	0.84	17.91
	TMO (I)	62.50	90.80	4.31	0.014*	0.015	0.55	1.41
	TMO (II)	8950	228.50	4.75	0.046***	0.007	0.73	4.78
	TMO Total	62.0	228.50	4.44	0.039***	0.004	0.72	4.04
	Overall Period	5.90	228.50	2.69	0.062***	0.004	0.81	6.48
Tamil Nadu	Pre TMO	38.60	45.60	3.60	0.002	0.014	0.14	0.23
	TMO (I)	32.40	46.00	3.69	0.022	0.011	0.22	2.30
	TMO (II)	28.00	23.10	3.48	-0.022	0.016	0.11	-2.24
	TMO Total	32.40	23.10	4.05	-0.028***	0.006	0.41	-2.76
	Overall Period	38.60	23.10	3.82	-0.009**	0.003	0.12	-0.98
Andhra Pradesh	Pre TMO	341.10	124.30	6.09	-0.053***	0.012	0.57	-5.14
	TMO (I)	122.80	107.50	4.92	-0.006*	0.005	0.46	-0.68
	TMO (II)	81.70	88.00	4.52	0.001	0.003	0.01	0.17
	TMO Total	122.80	88.00	4.96	-0.016***	0.002	0.63	-1.60
	Overall Period	341.80	88.00	5.82	-0.03***	0.002	0.81	-3.23
Orissa	Pre TMO	14.70	11.00	2.88	-0.033***	0.007	0.61	-3.34
	TMO (I)	11.10	2.40	2.29	-0.071***	0.022	0.41	-6.89
	TMO (II)	2.10	0.30	1.49	-0.152***	0.018	0.82	-14.18
	TMO Total	11.10	0.30	3.37	-0.128***	0.008	0.89	-12.02
	Overall Period	14.70	0.30	3.57	-0.076***	0.006	0.76	-7.35
Madhya Pradesh + Chhattisgarh	Pre TMO	562.30	501.00	6.07	-0.010*	0.008	0.34	-1.08
	TMO (I)	447.70	697.80	6.48	-0.008*	0.009	0.63	-0.87
	TMO (II)	441.30	755.40	6.38	0.020**	0.008	0.31	2.07
	TMO Total	447.70	755.40	6.34	0.008**	0.003	0.17	0.84
	Overall Period	562.30	755.40	6.09	0.011***	0.001	0.49	1.17
India	Pre TMO	1523.76	1726.36	2.96	0.014***	0.004	0.53	1.40

	TMO (I)	1263.69	3562.07	3.45	0.029***	0.003	0.73	2.94
	TMO (II)	1634.60	2015.36	4.03	0.037***	0.001	0.70	3.76
	TMO Total	1263.69	2015.36	5.63	0.048***	0.002	0.79	4.91
	Overall Period	1523.76	2015.36	5.96	0.049***	0.003	0.80	5.02

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability

** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

Compound annual growth of safflower production during different periods

Compound annual growth rate in production of safflower crop is presented in table 9 for India as well as major producing states. During the entire study period, all the states along with the country as a whole have shown decline in production with Andhra Pradesh having highest rate of decline in production to the extent of 7.35 per cent per annum. Only in the state of West Bengal positive growth in the production of safflower has been observed at the rate of 2.36 per cent per annum.

Table 9: Compound annual growth rate in production of safflower for different periods (000' tons)

States	Time period	Initial year observation	Final year observation	Constant	Trend coefficient	Standard error	R ²	CAGR (%)
Maharashtra	Pre TMO	110.30	248.70	4.45	0.090***	0.014	0.73	9.48
	TMO (I)	197.50	139.00	5.82	-0.056**	0.025	0.45	-5.42
	TMO (II)	116.00	21.40	5.33	-0.122**	0.024	0.64	-11.52
	TMO Total	197.50	21.40	5.88	0.008**	0.003	0.63	-0.87
	Overall Period	110.30	21.40	5.66	-0.028***	0.006	0.49	-2.84
Karnataka	Pre TMO	26.90	85.80	2.74	0.129***	0.016	0.81	13.81
	TMO (I)	143.20	72.80	4.79	-0.033**	0.015	0.45	-3.29
	TMO (II)	55.20	27.80	4.18	-0.056***	0.010	0.67	-5.53
	TMO Total	143.20	27.80	4.91	-0.049***	0.004	0.78	-4.80
	Overall Period	55.20	27.80	4.08	-0.002*	0.006	0.63	-0.26
Gujarat	Pre TMO	341.10	124.30	6.09	-0.053***	0.012	0.57	-5.14
	TMO (I)	122.80	107.50	4.92	-0.006*	0.005	0.58	-0.68
	TMO (II)	81.70	88.00	4.52	0.001	0.003	0.01	0.17
	TMO Total	122.80	88.00	4.96	-0.016***	0.002	0.63	-1.60
	Overall Period	341.80	88.00	5.82	-0.03***	0.002	0.81	-3.23
Andhra Pradesh	Pre TMO	14.70	11.00	2.88	-0.033***	0.007	0.61	-3.34
	TMO (I)	11.10	2.40	2.29	-0.071***	0.022	0.41	-6.89
	TMO (II)	2.10	0.30	1.49	-0.152***	0.018	0.82	-14.18
	TMO Total	11.10	0.30	3.37	-0.128***	0.008	0.89	-12.02
	Overall Period	14.70	0.30	3.57	-0.076***	0.006	0.76	-7.35
West Bengal	Pre TMO	0.12	0.30	-1.75	0.019	0.024	0.044	2.01
	TMO (I)	0.40	0.12	-0.48	-0.115***	0.010	0.88	-10.91
	TMO (II)	0.30	1.00	-1.36	0.048**	0.015	0.62	7.87
	TMO Total	0.40	1.00	-1.58	0.030**	0.011	0.49	3.04
	Overall Period	0.13	1.00	-1.83	0.023**	0.005	0.67	2.36
Madhya Pradesh	Pre TMO	153.90	347.90	4.70	0.094***	0.013	0.78	9.85
	TMO (I)	352.50	220.60	6.16	-0.048**	0.019	0.31	-4.73
	TMO (II)	178.50	55.30	5.57	-0.078**	0.015	0.64	-7.57
	TMO Total	352.50	55.30	6.25	-0.055***	0.006	0.72	-5.44
	Overall Period	153.90	55.30	5.83	-0.018**	0.005	0.49	-1.79
India	Pre TMO	850.69	975.06	4.26	0.043***	0.004	0.63	4.39
	TMO (I)	1032.53	1532.07	3.69	0.050***	0.003	0.71	5.12
	TMO (II)	986.46	549.63	4.03	-0.037***	0.042	0.66	-3.63
	TMO Total	1032.53	549.63	4.26	-0.047***	0.007	0.79	-4.59
	Overall Period	850.69	549.63	4.86	-0.049***	0.029	0.71	-4.78

*** shows significant at 1 per cent level of probability

** shows significant at 5 per cent level of probability

* shows significant at 10 per cent level of probability

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